

Deep Mixed Precision for Hyperspectral Image Classification

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Abstract Hyperspectral images (HSIs) record scenes at different wavelength channels, providing detailed spatial and spectral information. How to storage and process this high-dimensional data plays a vital role in many practical applications, where classification technologies have emerged as excellent processing tools. However, their high computational complexity and energy requirements bring some challenges. Adopting low-power consumption architectures and deep learning (DL) approaches has to provide acceptable computing capabilities without reducing accuracy demand. However, most DL architectures employ single-precision (FP32) to train models, and some big DL architectures will have a limitation on memory and computation resources. This can negatively affect the network learning process. This letter leads these challenges by using mixed precision into DL architectures for HSI classification to speed up the training process and reduce the memory consumption/access. Proposed models are evaluated on four widely-used data sets. Also, low and high-power consumption devices are compared, considering NVIDIA Jetson Xavier and Titan RTX GPUs, to evaluate the proposal viability in on-board processing devices. Obtained results demonstrate the efficiency and effectiveness of these models within HSI classification task for both devices. Source codes:<https://github.com/mhaut/CNN-MP-HSI>

Keywords Hyperspectral image · Deep learning · Mixed Precision

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1 Introduction

As one of the most important data sources in remote sensing, hyperspectral imaging (HSI) provides rich and detailed spectral information about different materials on the earth surface. This spectral information has been widely used in a vast number of [applications](#), such as image super-resolution [13] or spectral unmixing [24], among others. By analyzing the continuous and narrow-band spectral signatures contained into pixels, different land cover categories can potentially be precisely differentiated. In this context, supervised classification plays a vital role in analysing and processing the HSI information. Moreover, the main interest of supervised classifiers lies in their guided training procedure, where labelled training samples are used to fit the model parameters. As a result, supervised methods achieve much higher precision values than unsupervised methods [6]. [Therefore](#), many supervised methods have been extensively exploited in many practical activities, including land changes monitoring or natural resources management [1]. However, the accuracy of supervised classifiers is highly affected when the number of available training samples is limited in relation to the (high) data dimensionality, [which is quite common in HSI due to](#) the high cost and workload involved in the expert annotation. This may cause incomplete training process that easily [introduces](#) overfitting.

To address the aforementioned issues, several deep models have been developed [reaching](#) some breakthrough accomplishment in ML. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have demonstrated to be highly accurate techniques due to their ability for automatically extracting discriminative features. For instance, Yue *et al.* [26] proposed a CNN3D to classify HSI data in consideration of spectral-spatial information. To further enhance the accuracy, many improvements have been [include](#) to the CNN framework, [such as](#) Paoletti *et al.* [18] [who](#) presented a fast end-to-end CNN3D in the consideration of the full spectral signatures contained in HSI data to improve the classification accuracy. However, CNN models still encounter some limitations due to the depth and the high number of [trainable](#) parameters, and the intrinsic characteristics of HSI data. Specially, CNN models [require an important amount](#) of training data to adjust their weights appropriately. To overcome the limitations, different [strategies](#) have been proposed, such as semisupervised and active learning (AL) techniques [7], which address the lack of training samples problem by increasing the quantity-quality [trade-off](#) of the training samples, respectively. Particularly, these techniques are quite effective for discovering feature representativeness and discriminativeness. Other algorithms are based on residual and dense connections [20]. These techniques can alleviate both loss of information and vanishing gradient problems of very complex and deep architectures. Finally, there is a third type of algorithms based on new information routing techniques, such as capsule modules [19] [which were proposed to overcome the CNN limitations when](#) exploring the spatial relationships among learned instantiation parameters, such as size, perspective and orientation.

Despite these progresses, CNN-based models still face some challenges when dealing with HSI data. For instance, their training and inference stages require processing thousands of millions of floating point operations, involving a large number of parameters and data variables which are in single-precision format. This increases the storage and compute requirements, which are already high because of the large spectral dimension. As a result, deep HSI classifiers require powerful and usually expensive computer resources, which are high power-consuming and therefore usually located in processing centres at the ground segment. As a result, developing on-board processing solutions is quite difficult, as computing platforms usually have limitations in both memory capacity and energy consumption [5]. In this context, adapting these deep models to reduce both memory and computing requirements is mandatory, not only to optimise computing times, but also to deploy them on low-power-consumption platforms, allowing on-board processing.

This paper adopts the newest trends in deep learning (DL), combining single (FP32) and half-precision (FP16) data and arithmetic formats to alleviate the high computational burden involved by deep HSI classification models while maintaining the accuracy performance [17,9]. Indeed, this paper conducts an extensive comparative between several CNN-based models with single and mixed precision strategies by taking advantages of GPU architecture. Moreover, it provides a comparative between high and low-power consumption devices, comparing the NVIDIA GPUs Titan RTX and Jetson Xavier. Implemented HSI classifiers exhibit: i) a high speed within math-intensive operations, where Tensor Cores optimize the convolution and matrix operations, and ii) a significant reduction in both memory consumption and memory access times.

2 Background

The success of CNN lies in the application of local kernels onto small patches of the input, which filter the presence of specific features, followed by an activation function that obtains the neuronal response to those features:

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathcal{H}(\mathbf{X} * \mathbf{W} + \mathbf{b}), \text{ with } y_{i,j,t} = \sum_{\hat{i}, \hat{j}, \hat{t}} x_{i+\hat{i}, j+\hat{j}, \hat{t}} w_{\hat{i}, \hat{j}, \hat{t}, t} + b_t \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N \times C}$ and $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times M \times K}$ are the input and output volumes, and $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{P \times P \times C \times K}$ and $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^K$ defines the kernel weights and bias vector. Naturals $\hat{t} \in [1, C]$ and $t \in [1, K]$ index the input and output channels, $i, j \in [1, N]$ and $\hat{i}, \hat{j} \in [1, P]$ are indexing the output and kernel elements along the spatial dimension, and \tilde{i}, \tilde{j} are the re-centered spatial indices indexing the input. \mathcal{H} defines the activation function. From Eq. (1), it is easy to estimate the number of parameters and FLOPs performed by L convolution layers:

$$\text{Params.} : \sum_{l=1}^L P_l^2 \times C_l \times K_l, \quad \text{FLOPs}_l : K_l \times N_l^2 \times C_l \times P_l^2 \quad (2)$$

This results in a massive amount of both trainable parameters and operations, making CNNs computational-intensive models. Important efforts have been conducted in order to reduce this drawback [14,4]. Some approaches attempt to lighten the model by dividing the standard layer into separable depth/point-wise layers [23]. In [22], authors combine separable layers with shift-based operations to simulate the movement of the spatial features at each map, reducing the number of parameters and therefore the operations performed. Also, [2] proposes a lightweight model based on separable convolutions, combining the deep feature extraction with an approximate rank-order clustering. Furthermore, [21] divides the layer into a lighter convolution operation combined with a set of cheaper linear transformations. However, these models operate on FP32, without taking advantage of the benefits of mixed precision between FP32 and FP16.

3 Methodology

3.1 NVIDIA Hardware Optimization

The great demand for high performance devices for parallel and massive data processing has produced a wide range of GPUs, with different features and capabilities, which are pretty useful for many computationally-intensive applications. In particular, the NVIDIA *Turing* architecture [10] is quite interesting, as it encodes an instruction and its control information with 128 bits, following the *Volta* encoding format, while previous architectures, such as *Pascal* and *Maxwell*, employ 64 bits for an instruction information and 64 bits of control. In this sense, *Turing* uses 91 bits for the instruction information and 23 bits for the control, while the remaining 14 are not used. Regarding memory, *Turing* combines L1 data cache and shared memory, following *Volta* model. The L2 cache is similar to previous generations, as it is unified for data, instructions, and memory. Table 1 provides a comparison between different NVIDIA GPUs architecture generations. Therefore, *Turing* provides both a

Table 1: Comparative between several NVIDIA GPUs architectures

Architectures (sizes in KiB)					
Feature	<i>Turing</i>	<i>Volta</i>	<i>Pascal</i>	<i>Maxwell</i>	<i>Kepler</i>
L2 cache	4096	6144	4096	2048	1536
L1.5 cache	46	64	64	32	-
L1 cache	144	256	32	32	48
L0 cache	16	12	12	-	-
Registers	64	64	128	64	255
Tensor Cores	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗

new streaming multiprocessor (SM) and a new memory system architectures, improving the efficiency and performance for massive parallel applications, which is quite interesting for optimizing DNNs for HSI classification. For instance, the *Turing* SM enables concurrent execution of FP32 and

INT32 operations by including independent integer and floating-point math datapaths, while the different memory-level paths have been unified, providing a bigger and faster L2 cache and including support for the GDDR6 memory technology to increase the bandwidth. In addition, the architecture enhances the specialized execution units for matrix operations, called *Turing* Tensor Cores (TTCs). These TTCs are designed for the multiplication of two matrices, and the accumulation of a third matrix, and provide multi-precision computing (considering FP32, FP16, INT8 and INT4). This property facilitates the combination of different precision formats (the so-called mixed precision) when training neural networks, which significantly accelerates arithmetic calculations and reduces the memory accesses/consumption, while keeping constant the accuracy results.

To properly optimize those operations, a high-performance CUDA SDK is provided, which includes the TensorRT as the inference optimizer. It takes a trained network (i.e., a network definition and the corresponding set of trained parameters) and produces a highly optimized runtime engine which performs the inference stage for the selected network. Finally, previous architectures can be built in embedded systems and other devices, such as the low-power-consumption and heterogeneous multi-processor NVIDIA Tegra models. For instance, the Tegra K1, TK1 and TK2 models use the *Kepler* architecture with a maximum of 365 GFLOPS and 951 MHz frequency, while Tegra X1 uses the *Maxwell* architecture. This model includes the half-precision and it is composed of 256 GPU cores with a maximum of 1298 GFLOPS for FP16, 649 GFLOPS for FP32 and 1267 MHz frequency. Its successor, Tegra X2, changes the GPU architecture to *Pascal* with a maximum of 1465 GFLOPS for FP16, 750 GFLOPS for FP32 and 1267 MHz frequency. Tegra Xavier adopts the *Volta* architecture with a maximum of 2820 GFLOPS for FP16, 1410 GFLOPS for FP32 and 1377 MHz frequency. Finally, although it is not yet publicly available to the market, Clara AGX models will implement the *Turing* architecture, considering the previous Xavier computing module to produce an optimal inference using TTCs.

3.2 Mixed Precision strategy

As noted above, DL training systems use the FP32 format, which involves reading and computing millions of parameters represented by 32 bits. As a result, DNNs exhibit high time and energy costs. In this sense, the current trend is to reduce the memory footprint while optimizing the memory load of the model in order to speed the computation. This can be done by rearranging the data [25] or shrinking the data size [17]. In particular, casting some data/operations from FP32 to FP16 calculation is quite interesting, saving memory while increasing the speed up. Therefore, this paper studies the performance of several DNNs considering single and mixed precision [17]. Proposed implementations are based on TTC behaviour, where the DNNs performance is accelerated by transforming the vast majority of

Fig. 1: Mixed precision training. Red and green paths represent FP32 and FP16 formats, respectively. During forward step $\mathbf{X}^{(l-1)}$ and $\mathbf{X}^{(l)}$ denote the input and output activations of l -th layer, and $\mathbf{W}^{(l)}$ its kernel-weights. During backpropagation, $\partial\mathbf{X}^{(l)}$ and $\delta^{(l)}$ are the activation and weights gradients.

the mathematical computations into half-precision, while ensuring that no task-specific accuracy is degraded by identifying those steps/computations that require single precision. Hereof, hidden layers cast their FP32 inputs into FP16 format to conduct FP16 calculations, resulting into a FP16 outputs. Moreover, to prevent model accuracy loss, the following three techniques are implemented [9]: i) maintaining a FP32 copy of weights, which accumulates the gradients after each optimizer step; ii) loss-scaling to avoid vanishing gradient because data truncation, and iii) FP16 arithmetic with accumulation in FP32. These techniques are detailed below.

During training step, data tensors (model weights, activations and gradients values) are cast into FP16 format, which implies that all arithmetic operations will be performed in FP16 too. This enables a faster operation, consuming less memory bandwidth. Eq. (3) shows the castings for forward (3a) and backward (3b) steps formulation:

$$\forall l \in [1, \dots, L], \left(\mathbf{Z}^{(l)} = \mathbf{W}^{(l)} + \mathbf{b}^{(l)} \right)_{FP32 \rightarrow FP16} \quad (3a)$$

$$\forall l \in [1, \dots, L], \left(\mathbf{W}_{new}^{(l)} = \mathbf{W}_{old}^{(l)} - \mu \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \mathbf{W}^{(l)}} \right)_{FP32 \rightarrow FP16} \quad (3b)$$

where $\mathbf{W}^{(l)}$ denotes the corresponding weights of the l -th layer, μ is the learning rate and $\partial\mathcal{L}/\partial\mathbf{W}^{(l)}$ the weight derivation, considering \mathcal{L} as the loss function and L the number of layers.

However, FP16 has some disadvantages which can produce an incorrect training. Indeed, FP16-data is composed of 16 bits, which are organized as follows: the first bit is the sign bit, which gives +1 or -1, then the following 5 bits are used to code an exponent between -14 and 15, while the fraction part

comprises the remaining 10 bits. Compared to FP32, it has a smaller range of possible values (from 2^{-24} to $(2 - 2^{-10})2^{15}$, where normalized value exponents range into $[-14, 15]$) but also a smaller offset. As a result smaller magnitudes than 2^{-24} are ignored and discarded. This produces severe precision errors, such as an incorrect weight update, zero gradients, or infinite/NaN values in the loss or activations.

To counteract this, first a FP32 copy of weights is kept. Although the FP16-weights are used during the forward and backward steps of each iteration to halve the memory consumption and bandwidth, weights updating is conducted over the FP32-weights to avoid the truncated/zero weights. Then, updated weights are cast back to FP16 to perform the next forward-backward steps. Regarding the gradients, the loss is scaled up by factor $s = 8$ before the backpropagation, pushing it into large values to prevent potentially truncated/zero gradients, and then a reverse scaling is applied before the weight update. In this sense, the softmax of the model tail should be represented in FP32 to avoid numerical error calculations. Eq. (4) shows the loss scaling formulation for the weight update:

$$\mathbf{W}_{FP32} = \mathbf{W}_{FP16} - \mu \frac{1}{s} \left(s \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \mathbf{W}_{FP16 \rightarrow FP32}} \right) \quad (4)$$

This simple and cheap solution allows the computation of small gradients, [avoiding artificial vanishing problems and poor weights to be learnt, and hence, improving the convergence of the model as demonstrated in \[16,17\]](#). Finally, DNN can include some operations that required FP32 precision to avoid the uncertainties (in particular batch-normalization and softmax layers). Indeed, DNN performs vector dot-products, reductions and point-wise operations, where the FP16 vector dot-product has to accumulate the partial products into a FP32 value and then convert it to FP16 before writing to memory in order to maintain the accuracy precision. This can be easily conducted by the TTCs. Moreover, large reductions which perform the sum of a vector elements should be done in FP32 following the same procedure. Fig. (1) provides the mixed precision training flowchart.

As we can observe, the DNN has to detect the operation types that should be represented in FP32 because their FP16 representation do not provide the desired accuracy (for instance, the loss, softmax, and cross entropy functions). To do this, Apex Automatic Mixed Precision (AMP) [11] is used. Apex is an extension on PyTorch which takes care of tensor casting, ensuring that all arguments are of the same type. To ensure that castings are performed only once per iteration, it keeps an internal cache of all the casts of the parameters and reuses them. Moreover, it performs the FP32 copy of weights, computing forward and backward stages in FP16 and updating in FP32, and detecting those operations that should be executed on FP32 while most of computations are executed on FP16.

4 Experimental evaluation

To conduct the comparison between several DNNs for HSI classification in single and mixed precision formats, an X Generation Intel Core i9-9940X is employed, which is composed of 14 cores (28 with multi-task processing) running at 4.40GHz with a 19M cache. The GPU is an NVIDIA Titan RTX with 24GB of GDDR6 memory, 4608 cores and 576 *Turing* Tensor Cores. Also the NVIDIA Jetson AGX Xavier is tested, with an ARM CPU composed of 8 cores running at 2.5GHz with 16GB-RAM and 512 *Volta* tensor cores.

Moreover, four widely used HSI data sets [3,12] have been used in our experiments, i.e., Indian Pines (IP), Salinas Valley (SV), Kennedy Space Center (KSC) and the University of Pavia (UP).

- **IP** has 145×145 pixels with 20m spatial resolution and 224 spectral bands in the wavelength range from 0.4 to 2.5 μm . We remove 24 bands due to water absorption and null values, keeping 200 bands.
- **PU** has 610×340 pixels and 103 spectral bands in the wavelength range from 0.43 to 0.86 μm and 1.3 m spatial resolution.
- **SV** has 224 spectral bands and 512×217 pixels with a 3.7 m spatial resolution in the range from 0.4 to 2.5 μm . We remove some noisy and water absorption bands from the original 224 bands, keeping 200 bands.
- **KSC** has 224 spectral bands and 512×614 pixels with a 18 m spatial resolution in the range from 0.4 to 2.5 μm . Again, we remove water absorption and low SNR bands, keeping 176 bands.

Overall (OA) and average accuracy (AA) and kappa coefficient (K) have been used to measure the accuracy performance. Also, the runtime (in seconds), number of parameters, memory consumption (in MB) and the processed-samples-per-second (PSPS) measurements have been adopted to evaluate the computational properties.

We compare the performance of several DNNs for HSI classification, considering single and mixed precision training and inference. [To address the experimentation we have selected the most innovative algorithms. Thus, effective algorithms previously tested on a broad set of algorithms from the HSI DL literature are used.](#) In particular the CNN2D and CNN2D+RO [8] have been used to perform spatial feature extraction (FE) and HSI classification, where the second one includes random occlusion data augmentation. [Regarding the scalability and consistency of our proposal,](#) the deeper and more complex PResNet model [20] is used to conduct deep spectral-spatial FE and HSI classification. Model setting specifications [8,20] have been followed. [These algorithms were previously tested over the same data sets mentioned above, maintaining a consistency in the evaluation conducted.](#)

Fig. 2 provides the OA evolution of CNN2D, CNN2D-RO and PResNet in single (SP_CNN2D, SP_CNN2D+RO and SP_PResNet) and automatic mixed precision (MP_CNN2D, MP_CNN2D+RO and MP_PResNet) when considering different amounts of training samples, in particular 5%, 10% and

Fig. 2: Overall accuracy (%) of SP_CNN2D, SP_CNN2D+RO and SP_PResNet and their mixed precision counterparts, MP_CNN2D, MP_CNN2D+RO and MP_PResNet, when considering different training percentages in IP, KSC, SV and PU scenes

Table 2: Accuracy performance over IP and PU scenes considering single and mixed precision. Also, number of parameters and training runtimes are provided

Class	Indian Pines						Pavia University					
	PResNet		CNN2D		CNN2D+RO		PResNet		CNN2D		CNN2D+RO	
	SP	MP	SP	MP	SP	MP	SP	MP	SP	MP	SP	MP
0	97.07	99.02	73.66	69.75	90.24	76.1	99.8	99.76	95.94	95.83	97.61	97.23
1	99.41	99.27	86.27	86.52	92.09	92.48	99.99	99.98	98.66	98.85	99.37	99.22
2	98.74	98.8	84.26	89.64	95.34	95.82	99.05	98.99	88.76	90.49	91.42	91.68
3	96.71	94.74	95.87	93.52	95.02	95.87	99.6	99.46	96.63	96.87	98.91	98.64
4	99.59	98.94	89.06	87.68	95.35	93.98	100.0	100.0	99.48	99.84	98.79	97.89
5	99.54	99.36	93.94	95.37	97.9	98.78	100.0	99.98	92.98	94.15	97.9	98.18
6	88.8	89.6	80.8	88.0	96.0	90.4	98.46	98.48	91.72	90.06	94.43	95.77
7	99.91	100.0	95.58	97.02	97.4	97.91	99.76	99.71	97.68	97.22	98.97	98.67
8	96.66	95.55	54.44	76.67	81.11	73.33	99.89	99.85	97.95	98.09	98.73	99.07
9	96.66	97.01	89.19	92.41	94.56	93.35	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	98.92	98.72	91.96	93.67	97.76	97.89	-	-	-	-	-	-
11	97.12	97.11	85.28	83.9	94.68	93.15	-	-	-	-	-	-
12	99.89	100.0	95.03	91.24	97.08	98.05	-	-	-	-	-	-
13	98.54	98.7	97.12	98.65	98.89	99.51	-	-	-	-	-	-
14	95.33	94.41	90.37	90.66	95.27	96.71	-	-	-	-	-	-
15	95.24	95.95	81.19	79.52	96.91	93.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
OA	98.49	98.38	90.51	91.82	96.06	96.05	99.82	99.79	96.65	96.87	98.28	98.18
AA	97.38	97.32	86.50	88.39	94.72	92.90	99.62	99.58	95.53	95.71	97.35	97.37
K(x100)	98.28	98.15	89.17	90.66	95.51	95.49	99.76	99.72	95.55	95.85	97.72	97.58
Tr. time (s)	265.27	256.6	224.77	218.57	233.72	222.69	674.73	600.1	385.04	331.69	397.6	341.12
Parameters	4.6M		1.1M		4.6M		1.1M		4.6M		1.1M	

15% of IP and KSC scenes, and 1%, 5% and 10% of SV and UP images. Focusing on FP32 implementations, SP_PResNet significantly outperforms the OA of CNN models (with the exception of KSC, due to the spatial complexity and intense spectral mixing of the image), while the SP_CNN2D+RO consequently improves the results of the conventional CNN2D, which is greatly affected by overfitting. This behaviour can be observed also between MP implementations, where MP_PResNet is able to extract highly discriminative feature representations, as it not only builds a more complex architecture but also considers the full spectral information. Comparing SP with MP implementations, each pair of networks reach close accuracy with slight variations, in particular SP_CNN2D and MP_CNN2D, where the second one usually reaches better OA, i.e., with MP, the problem of overfitting can be effectively reduced.

Table 2 provides a deeper study between both implementations, evaluating the accuracy in terms of OA, AA and Kappa values over IP (10% training data) and UP (5% training data). Once more, PResNet reaches the best accuracy values, and it is followed by CNN2D+RO model. Also, the pairs

of models achieve quite similar results, being sometimes slightly better the SP-version and others the MP (in particular the CNN2D). Focusing on the number of parameters, pairs of implementations exhibit also quite similar parameters, where the PResNet comprises more parameters than the other models. However, runtimes captured during training stage show that, despite having the same number of parameters (approximately), the MP-based implementation are faster than SP models, achieving also similar accuracy performances.

Fig. 3: Memory consumption and processed samples per second ratio on Titan RTX and Jetson Xavier devices considering PResNet

Finally, Fig. 3 provides the memory consumption and the PSpS ratios of both PResNet implementations considering every HSI dataset. Moreover, we compare both GPUs, evaluating the performance of typically high performance computing and low-power consumption devices. Regarding the Titan RTX, and focusing on the memory requirements, the same batch size [20] is used, where SV and IP scenes consume the most due their number of channels. However, MP_PResNet greatly reduces its memory consumption, where the FP32 copy of weights and the auxiliar FP32 variables barely represent a great effort compared to the large number of activations, which are stored in FP16. Moreover, the transformation of most operations to FP16 arithmetic significantly increases processing speed, while the reading/writing of FP16 tensors in memory has less impact. As a result, more samples can be processed per second, as we can observe in Fig. 3(b), which in turn allows the batch size to be increased. This behaviour can be also observed on Jetson Xavier device, where the MP-implementations process more samples per second. Comparing both devices, we can see that the processing ratios are quite similar, where the Titan RTX has a higher ratio because of its optimized Turing Tensor Cores, while the Jetson Xavier contains Volta Tensor Cores. This result demonstrates that mixed-precision is an useful technique to reduce the high computational and memory requirements of DNNs for HSI classification, effectively adjusting them to the hardware limitations imposed by potential on-board platforms, such as the Jetson Xavier.

5 Conclusions and future work

Most existing DL architectures use FP32 format for training, bringing a big burden for memory consumption/access. To address the issue, we exploit mixed precision over two GPU devices (Titan RTX and Jetson Xavier) to train several deep HSI classifiers. This can reduce memory consumption and the time spent on memory and arithmetic operations. Experimental results have revealed that MP-based implementations are quite effective and efficient in HSI classification. Moreover, the comparison between high and low-power consumption devices shows that it is an useful solution to reduce the computational and memory requirements, adapting the deep and complex models to the limitations imposed by the potential on-board platforms. [This provides interesting results for HSI classification in this type of devices where memory usage and workload computation are key factors, as demonstrated in recent studies on satellites devices \[15\].](#) Encouraged by these results, we will explore more DL models with mixed precision, exploring practical applications.

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